

Lab protocols to study Solute Carrier Transporters

Transfection to Generate BacMam Virus containing SLC transporter and small scale expression testing

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Authors	¹ David B. Sauer, ¹ Huanyu Li, ¹ Sagar Raturi, ¹ Andreea Scacioc, ¹ Tina Bohstedt, ¹ Abilasha Balakrishnan
Affiliations	¹ Centre for Medicines Discovery, University of Oxford. Oxford, UK

Protocol description

This protocol is used to transfect Sf9 insect cells with the bacmid produced previously. The transfection of the insect cells leads to the generation of baculoviral particles later used to transduce mammalian host cells for expressing the SLC transporter.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Sf9 cells (ThermoFisher, catalog Number: 11496-015)▪ Expi293F Cells (Life Technologies Limited, catalog number: A14528)▪ PEG10,000 (Sigma-Aldrich, catalog number 81280)
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Insect Genejuice (Merck-Sigma, catalog number 71259-4)▪ Sf-900 II SFM medium (ThermoFisher, catalog Number: 10902104)▪ FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium (ThermoFisher, catalog Number:12338-018)▪ Penicillin-Streptomycin (Life Technologies Limited, catalog number: 15140-122)▪ 24-well Clear TC-treated Multiple Well Plates (Costar, catalog number 3524)▪ Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), (ThermoFischer, catalogue number 10500064)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Microbiological Safety Cabinet - Class II▪ INFORS Multitron Cell CO₂ shaker incubator or INFORS Celltron shaker placed inside a static CO₂ incubator▪ Glas-Col shaker (Glas-Col, catalog number 107A DPMINC12)

Reagents setup

Procedure

Bacmid transfection of Sf9 cells

1. Thaw an aliquot of the heat-inactivated Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) stock a day before your experiment in the fridge at 4°C (not in a water bath).
2. Prepare cells one day in advance, by diluting the Sf9 cell count to $1.1 - 1.2 \times 10^6$ cells/mL in Sf-900 II serum free medium (SFM). This is to allow the cells to reach mid-log phase (cells cultures with $1.8 - 3.5 \times 10^6$ cells/ml density can be used).
3. On the day of transfection, dilute the mid-log phase Sf9 cells to 2×10^5 cells/mL in Sf-900 II SFM medium (use the medium from the same lot number) and dispense 1 mL diluted cells into each well of four 24-well tissue culture plates. Include one Insect GeneJuice only control and one cells only control. Incubate the plates at 27°C for 1 hour to allow cell attachment.
4. Mix 200 µL of Insect GeneJuice with 4 mL of Sf-900 II SFM medium in a 15 mL tube. Gently vortex for 10 seconds.
Note: Use 2 µL of Insect GeneJuice per well and calculate medium requirement accordingly. Dispense 40 µL of the mixture (prepared in step 3) into a 96-well sterile flat bottom microtitre plate.
Transfer 2 µL of recombinant bacmid DNA (at 0.1 - 2.0 µg/µL concentration).

Note: If the concentration is higher than this, dilute using sterile tris-EDTA buffer into each well and mix by shaking the plate gently. For lower concentrations, add more DNA up to 5 μ L.

5. Cover the microtitre plate with a plastic cover and incubate the DNA:Insect GeneJuice mixture inside the microbiological safety cabinet for a maximum of 15 minutes.
6. After incubation, add 160 μ L of Sf-900 II SFM medium to the mixture in step 6.
7. Aspirate the medium from cells in step 1 and add the 200 μ L mixture from step 7 gently onto the cells. Covering the plates to avoid drying.
8. Incubate for 4 hours in a humidified incubator at 27°C, and add 400 μ L of Sf-900 II SFM medium containing 2% FBS. Gently transfer the plate into a clean plastic bag to reduce the rate of evaporation (do not seal).
9. Incubate the cells at 27°C for 72 hours in a static incubator. In the cells only control, confluent growth of cells will be seen under the microscope, whereas wells with infected cells will be sub-confluent. Infected cells are usually larger and granulated compared to the uninfected cells.
10. After approximately 3 days, transfer all the liquid contents from the 24-well tissue culture plate into a sterile 96-deep well block and centrifuge at 1,500 x *g* for 20 minutes at room temperature. Collect the clear supernatant (<700 μ L) in another sterile 96-deep well block. This is the P0 virus stock, which is stored at 4°C away from light.
11. For amplification, Sf9 cells in Sf900-II SFM Medium at a density of 2 x 10⁶ cells/mL are required.
12. Just before infection, add 2% FBS to the cells and seed them in a 24-deep well block in a final volume of 3 mL per well.
13. Infect the cells with 120 μ L of P0 BV stock and incubate at 27°C while shaking at 450 rpm in a Glas-Col shaker for 66-72 hours.
14. Pellet the cells by centrifugation at 1500 x *g* for 20 min and harvest the supernatant by pipetting into a 96-deep well block. Store as P1 BV stock at 4°C in the dark.

Expression Testing (Transduction)

Prior to starting the expression testing protocol, prepare 20% (w/v) PEG solution by dissolving 200 g of PEG10,000 (Fluka) and 12 g of NaCl in 600 mL ddH₂O, stir and bring to a final volume of 1000 mL. Autoclave the solution, **mix during the cooling period to prevent a phase separation** and store at room temperature for up to 1 year.

1. Add 300 μ L of concentrated P1 virus (harvested in the step-14 of the previous section) into corresponding wells of four 24-deep well blocks (refer to Fig. 1). Alternatively, use 90 μ L of P2 virus (un-concentrated).
2. Add 75 μ L of the PEG solution to each well containing 300 μ L of P1 virus. Shake the 24-deep well blocks in Glas-Col set at 18°C for 5 min, 300 rpm and leave the blocks at 4°C overnight or up to a week if Expi293F cells are not ready.

3. The following day, shake the 24-deep well blocks in a Glas-Col set at 18°C for 30 min, 300 rpm and centrifuge the blocks at 3000 x *g* for 45 min.
4. Inside a microbiological safety cabinet, carefully pipette out the supernatant and discard (the virus is concentrated and settled at the bottom of the blocks – translucent pellet).
5. For 3 mL scale expression testing, prepare required amount of Expi293F cells at 2x10⁶ cells/mL supplemented with 5 mM sodium butyrate (1 M sodium butyrate stock is prepared in PBS (see separate protocol), filter sterilised and stored in aliquots at -20°C).
6. Seed the cells into each well of the 24-deep well blocks, at the density of 2 x 10⁶ cells/mL in FreeStyle 293 medium.
7. Incubate the blocks in a 30°C incubator with 8% CO₂ and shaking set at 200 to 250 rpm for 72 hours.
NOTE: Place on a Celltron shaker inside a CO₂ incubator with shaking at 200 rpm, or in a Multitron shaking incubator at 220 rpm.
8. Harvest the cells by centrifugation at 900 x *g* for 20 min then add 1 mL of cold PBS to wash, centrifuge at 900 x *g* for 20 min and remove the PBS.
9. Freeze the pellets at -80°C. The expression of the SLC transporter can be checked at this point by running the sample on a SDS-PAGE.

Additional notes

Data availability

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.